

A Strategy to Tune Acoustic Terminations of Single-Can Test-Rigs to Mimic Thermoacoustic Behavior of a Full Engine

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ABSTRACT

Thermoacoustic properties of can-annular combustors are commonly investigated by means of single-can test-rigs. To obtain representative results, it is crucial to mimic can-can coupling present in the full engine. However, current approaches either lack a solid theoretical foundation or are not practicable for high-pressure rigs. In the present study we employ Bloch-wave theory to derive reflection coefficients that correctly represent can-can coupling. We propose a strategy to impose such reflection coefficients at the acoustic terminations of a single-can test-rig by installing passive acoustic elements, namely straight ducts or Helmholtz resonators. In an iterative process, these elements are adapted to match the reflection coefficients for the dominant frequencies of the full engine. The strategy is demonstrated with a network model of a generic can-annular combustor and a 3D model of a realistic can-annular combustor configuration. For the latter we show that can-can coupling via the compressor exit plenum is negligible for frequencies sufficiently far away from plenum eigenfrequencies. Without utilizing previous knowledge of relevant frequencies or flame dynamics, the test-rig models are adapted within a few iterations and match the full engine with good accuracy. Using Helmholtz resonators for test-rig adaption turns out to be more viable than using straight ducts.

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NOMENCLATURE

a amplitude level

A cross section area ratio

BBC Bloch boundary condition

c speed of sound

d characteristic length

f, g acoustic Riemann invariants

F flame response

FTF flame transfer function

He Helmholtz number

ITA intrinsic thermoacoustic

l length

\mathcal{L} extension length

LC limit cycle

m Bloch-wave number / azimuthal mode order

n iteration number

N number of cans

p acoustic pressure

\dot{Q} heat release rate

r, ϕ, z radial, azimuthal, axial coordinate

R reflection coefficient

\mathcal{R} equivalent reflection coefficient

s saturation factor

S cross section area

u acoustic velocity

\boldsymbol{x} position vector

Z acoustic impedance

Δ relative difference

ν frequency

ρ density

σ modal growth rate

ω angular frequency

INTRODUCTION

Thermoacoustic combustion instabilities are a major concern in the development of new low emission gas turbine combustors. Arising from constructive feedback between unsteady heat release and acoustics, these instabilities may result in large-amplitude oscillations of acoustic quantities, which can cause increased emission levels or even structural damage [1].

Latest generation land-based gas turbines are often equipped with a can-annular combustion system. In this combustor type a number of cans are arranged equidistantly around the circumference of the engine. The individual cans are coupled acoustically by a large upstream plenum that is fed by the gas turbine compressor and thus called compressor exit plenum. On the downstream side the cans are coupled via a small annular gap in front of the first turbine stator [2].

From a thermoacoustic point of view, this coupling is of particular interest although it is weak. It gives rise to azimuthal modes, which involve multiple cans and extend over the entire circumference of the engine. Several studies have characterized this coupling [2–4] and its importance regarding thermoacoustics of the entire engine [5–9]. Generally, due to the coupling of the individual cans, the thermoacoustic properties of an entire can-annular combustor can not be directly represented by a single-can system.

However, full scale numerical or experimental investigations of the thermoacoustic properties of an entire can-annular combustion system are extremely expensive and thus not feasible in the design phase of a new combustor. Typically in the late design phase, the thermoacoustic properties of the full engine are explored by means of single-can or single-sector test-rigs [5, 6, 10]. A variety of approaches are used to mimic can-can coupling in such single-can test-rigs. A commonly applied method is to extend the up- and downstream termination of the test-rig by straight ducts [6, 10, 11]. This, however, should be seen as an ad-hoc approach without solid

theoretical foundation. Another possibility to at least account for some modes resulting from can-can coupling is to employ two-can test-rigs [12], which obviously implies high effort.

More elaborate numerical approaches take into account the equivalent reflection coefficients that a single can is exposed to in the full can-annular system [13]. If these reflection coefficients can be imposed at the up- and downstream end of a single-can test-rig, it mimics the thermoacoustics of the entire engine. In numerical simulations this has already been exploited to simulate an entire can-annular combustor by resolving only one single can [14].

In experimental test-rigs, active control methods could in principle be used to impose the appropriate reflection coefficients [15–17]. However, in high-pressure single-can test-rigs of applied can-annular combustors this approach seems difficult to implement, because of generally limited access and the hot gas environment.

The present study instead focuses on test-rig adaption by passive acoustic elements. We critically assess the common practice of accounting for can-can coupling by extending the up- and downstream termination of test-rigs by straight ducts. In order to refine the current approach we propose and scrutinize an iterative adaption strategy to match the theoretically derived equivalent reflection coefficients with passive acoustic elements. We finally discuss two acoustic element types - straight ducts and Helmholtz resonators - that might be employed within the proposed strategy and apply them to adapt thermoacoustic models of single-can test-rigs. The present study reveals that test-rig adaption using duct extensions is not practical.

The paper is structured as follows: In the following section we recall the application of Bloch-wave theory in the context of thermoacoustics. We employ it to derive the equivalent reflection coefficients for a single can at a given azimuthal mode order. In the third section we discuss appropriate passive acoustic elements to mimic the equivalent reflection coefficients and propose an iterative adaption strategy. In the following sections, the proposed strategy is applied to a network model of a generic can-annular combustor adapted using straight ducts and a 3D model of a realistic can-annular combustor adapted using Helmholtz resonators. After a discussion of the expected importance of effects that are neglected in the present thermoacoustic models, a conclusion is drawn in the final section.

Figure 1: Generic can-annular combustor. Cans are coupled at up- and downstream side via compressor exit plenum and annular gap. R_{turb} and R_{comp} denote reflection coefficients of turbine inlet and compressor exit.

EQUIVALENT REFLECTION COEFFICIENTS COMPUTED FROM BLOCH-WAVE THEORY

Within this section we present the reflection coefficients up- and downstream of a single can in a can-annular combustor for a given azimuthal mode order m . These reflection coefficients lump the acoustic response of all remaining cans of the engine. The situation is sketched in Fig. 1 for a generic multi-can combustor. The considered single can is marked by the red dashed box, the equivalent reflection coefficients $\mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ are defined at its up- and downstream termination. Provided plane acoustic waves, the reflection coefficients are defined as the ratio of the down- and upstream traveling acoustic Riemann-Invariants $f = \hat{p}/\rho c + \hat{u}$ and $g = \hat{p}/\rho c - \hat{u}$ and are related to the acoustic impedance Z at the respective positions by

$$\mathcal{R}_{m,u} = \frac{f_u}{g_u} = \frac{Z_u + 1}{Z_u - 1}, \quad \mathcal{R}_{m,d} = \frac{g_d}{f_d} = \frac{Z_d - 1}{Z_d + 1}. \quad (1)$$

In general, $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ (with $x \hat{=} u/d$) in Fig. 1 depend on the thermoacoustic properties of the remaining cans. Therefore, in the most general case, the acoustic properties and especially flame dynamics of all individual cans have to be known in order to compute $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$.

However, typical can-annular combustors feature a discrete rotational symmetry, where the whole combustor consists of a number of N identical sectors arranged equidistantly around the circumference of the engine. These sectors - marked with the black dashed box in Fig. 1 and in the following denoted as “unit cells” - comprise one single can and the corresponding sector of the compressor exit plenum and the annular gap in front of the first turbine stage. For such a rotationally symmetric configuration, the equivalent reflection coefficients for a given azimuthal mode order m can be computed by utilizing Bloch-wave theory [18, 19]. As shown in the following, in this case $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ are only dependent on the elements coupling the individual cans and the degree of symmetry N and are independent of the thermoacoustics of the individual cans.

Mensah et al. [19] showed that the (thermo-)acoustic eigenmodes of discrete rotationally symmetric systems can be computed efficiently by utilizing Bloch-wave theory [18]. The eigenmodes \hat{p} of a can-annular combustor can thus be written as

$$\hat{p}(\mathbf{x}) = \Psi(\mathbf{x}) e^{im\phi}, \text{ with} \quad (2)$$

$$m = -(N/2 - 1), \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots, N/2 - 1, N/2.$$

Here, $\mathbf{x} = (r, \phi, z)$ is the position vector comprised of the radial, circumferential and axial coordinate, Ψ is a function that - for a given eigenmode - is identical in all N unit cells, m is called the Bloch-wave number. For low frequencies relevant in the present context, the absolute value $|m|$ of the Bloch-wave number is equivalent to the azimuthal mode order [19] and both terms are used synonymously in the following.

The (thermo-)acoustic eigenmodes expressed by Eqn. (2) can be classified into three types: azimuthally spinning modes with Bloch-wave numbers of $m = \pm 1, \dots, \pm(N/2 - 1)$, purely axial modes with $m = 0$ and so-called “push-pull” modes with $m = N/2$. The latter only exist for combustors with an even number of cans and are characterized by an acoustic pressure and velocity field of alternating signs in adjacent cans [13, 14]. Except for axial modes with $m = 0$, which feature identical pressure fields in all sectors, all other mode types result from coupling of the individual

unit cells. Thus, a single-can test-rig, where this coupling is not accounted for will only show modes of azimuthal order $m = 0$.

For applied can-annular combustors the mean flow in azimuthal direction is negligible. Provided discrete rotational symmetry, such a system features also reflection symmetry. In this case, the azimuthally spinning modes appear as degenerate pairs, where modes with Bloch-wave numbers of opposite sign merely differ by their direction of rotation. For the following derivations we can therefore limit our considerations to non-negative m [14, 19].

Without loss of generality we consider a unit cell centered at $\phi = 0$ and extended over an azimuthal angle $\phi = [-\pi/N, \pi/N]$. By definition, $\Psi(\mathbf{x})$ is identical in each unit cell. As the pressure is continuous across the interfaces connecting two unit cells (marked blue in Fig. 1), $\Psi(\mathbf{x})$ at the left and right boundary of the unit cell has to be equal [13]

$$\Psi\left(r, \phi = -\frac{\pi}{N}, z\right) = \Psi\left(r, \phi = \frac{\pi}{N}, z\right). \quad (3)$$

Combining Eqn. (3) with Eqn. (2) leads to a quasi-periodic boundary condition - called Bloch boundary condition (BBC) - for the acoustic pressure [19]

$$\hat{p}\left(r, \phi = \frac{\pi}{N}, z\right) = \hat{p}\left(r, \phi = -\frac{\pi}{N}, z\right) e^{im\frac{2\pi}{N}}. \quad (4)$$

Assuming that discrete rotational symmetry holds, a given azimuthal mode order m of the full can-annular combustor is completely represented by a single unit cell with BBC at the coupling interfaces, as sketched in Fig. 2. The equivalent reflection coefficients $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ defined at the in-/outlet of a single can are in this case independent of the remaining cans. They only depend on the acoustics of the coupling parts, i.e. the annular gap and the compressor exit plenum, the acoustic termination towards turbine R_{turb} and compressor R_{comp} , and the azimuthal mode order m and the number of cans N . $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ can thus be computed from an acoustic model that comprises

Figure 2: Definition of $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ at the in-/outlet of a single can. $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ are dependent on the azimuthal distance d of two cans and the cross sections of can S_c , annular gap S_a and compressor exit plenum S_p .

these coupling parts and BBC. This strategy has already been applied by Ghirardo et al. [13] to compute the equivalent reflection coefficient of a generic can outlet section.

The equivalent reflection coefficients defined in this way are valid for a given mode order m . They may be interpreted as the cumulative acoustic response of all remaining cans for a given azimuthal mode order, i.e. they represent the response of a certain synchronization pattern across all cans.

Equivalent reflection coefficients of a generic can-annular combustor

In order to discuss the general features of the equivalent reflection coefficients, Figure 3 shows $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ of a generic can-annular system with $N = 16$ cans for all azimuthal mode orders m . The shown $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ was computed using an acoustic network model similar as shown in Fig. 6. For simplicity, the acoustic termination towards turbine and compressor are assumed to be ideal sound hard walls with $R_{turb} = R_{comp} = 1$. $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ crucially depend on the area ratio A of annular gap and can ($A = S_a/S_c$) or plenum and can ($A = S_p/S_c$), respectively. Figure 3 shows the phase of the reflection coefficients for $A = 20$ (top) and $A = 0.06$ (bottom). The former is representative of the plenum/can transition (corresponds to $\mathcal{R}_{m,u}$), the latter is typical for the transition can/annular gap (corresponds to $\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$). Due to rotational and reflectional symmetry, no acoustic energy is exchanged between individual cans. Thus, the gain of $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ only depends on the gain of R_{turb} and R_{comp} . In the present case the gain $|\mathcal{R}_{m,x}|$ is thus uniformly unity for all mode orders and therefore not shown.

The phase of \mathcal{R}_m of all azimuthal mode orders m is plotted versus the Helmholtz-number $He = \omega d/c$, where ω is the angular frequency, c the speed of sound and d the azimuthal distance of the individual cans. In the zero-frequency limit the equivalent reflection coefficient behaves like

Figure 3: $\angle \mathcal{R}_m$ of generic 16-can combustor with two different area ratios $A = 20$ (top) and $A = 0.06$ (bottom) plotted vs. Helmholtz-number He .

a wall $\mathcal{R}_{m=0} = 1$ for $m = 0$ and like an ideal open end $\mathcal{R}_{m \neq 0} = -1$ for all other mode orders [13]. For $He = 2\pi \frac{m}{N}$, which correspond to purely azimuthal modes of order m that are only active in the plenum or the annular gap, the corresponding equivalent reflection coefficient equals $\mathcal{R}_m = 1$. For $He = \pi$, at which the distance d of two cans equals half a wavelength, Bloch-symmetry necessitates pressure nodes at the can centers for $m \neq N/2$, corresponding to an equivalent reflection coefficient $\mathcal{R}_{m \neq N/2} = -1$ [20]. In typical can-annular systems, $He = \pi$ is the cut-on frequency of transversal modes inside the cans. The validity of the 1D model employed here is thus questionable for $He > \pi$. However, the frequency range of interest in the present context is $He < \pi/4$.

For large area ratios A (top plot of Fig. 3), typical for the transition compressor-plenum/can, the equivalent reflection coefficient essentially represents an ideal open end with $\mathcal{R}_m \approx -1$ for a wide frequency range. Only in the vicinity of pure plenum modes of the respective azimuthal order \mathcal{R}_m deviates from the ideal open end. This indicates that for typical area ratios and for frequencies sufficiently far away from pure plenum modes the compressor exit plenum is essentially decoupled from the individual cans. \mathcal{R}_m of higher azimuthal mode orders may thus be approximated with $\mathcal{R}_{m=0}$.

For small area ratios A (bottom plot of Fig. 3), typical for the transition can/annular-gap, the general behavior of the equivalent reflection coefficients is similar. However, especially for fre-

quencies $He < \pi/4$, the individual \mathcal{R}_m are more distinct from each other, compared to \mathcal{R}_m for large A . This indicates that for this frequency range the coupling of individual cans via the annular gap with small A is more important than the coupling via the compressor exit plenum with large A . This preliminary result will be confirmed later by considering a realistic 3D configuration.

Overall, the phase of the equivalent reflection coefficients of individual mode orders m are closely spaced for both large and small A . This is a consequence of the weak coupling of individual cans for extreme values of A characteristic of can-annular combustors. It leads to clustering of eigenmodes with different m , because the reflection coefficient at the can entry and exit are similar for all m [8, 13]. For intermediate values of $A \sim 1$, $\angle \mathcal{R}_m$ of individual mode orders would be more distinct, resulting from stronger coupling.

The objective of the present work is to provide a strategy to investigate the thermoacoustics of a can-annular combustor by means of a single-can test-rig. If the equivalent reflection coefficients $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ can be imposed at the up- and downstream termination of the single-can test-rig, it will represent a given mode order m of the full engine and will have identical thermoacoustic properties. In the following section we discuss two types of passive acoustic elements that might be used to approximate $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$.

PASSIVE ACOUSTIC ELEMENTS TO APPROXIMATE EQUIVALENT REFLECTION COEFFICIENT

As shown in Fig. 3, the ensemble of cans reflects acoustic waves with a certain phase shift, which depends on frequency ω and azimuthal mode order m . The general idea of the present work is to approximate this phase shift for a given azimuthal mode order m with passive acoustic elements. A common practice to account for can-can coupling in single-can test-rigs is to extend the (up- and) downstream termination of the test-rig by straight ducts. In order to critically assess - and improve - this current practice, we investigate how a straight duct extension can be used to approximate the equivalent reflection coefficients. The second element we consider is a Helmholtz-type resonator.

Figure 4 shows schematically how the two considered elements should be installed in a test-

M. Haeringer, GTP-20-1545

Figure 4: Matching $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ of the full engine by extending the single-can test-rig with straight ducts (top) and by installing Helmholtz-resonators at the in-/outlet (bottom).

rig. The passive acoustic elements have to be adapted such that the phase of test-rig and equivalent reflection coefficient

$$\angle R_{x,rig}(\omega_d) \stackrel{!}{=} \angle \mathcal{R}_{m,x}(\omega_d) \quad (5)$$

match for the design frequency ω_d . As mentioned in the previous section, the gain $|\mathcal{R}_{m,x}|$ depends on the gain $|R_{comp/turb}|$ and is identical for all mode orders m . It is thus crucial that the considered elements do not affect the gain of the test-rig reflection coefficient $R_{x,rig}$. As the gain of R_{turb} is determined by the mean flow through the first turbine stator vanes [21], the duct extension used to shift the outlet termination $R_{comp,turb}$ must have a constant cross section. The Helmholtz resonator in turn must be designed for a minimum damping rate, i.e. it should be operated sufficiently far away from its eigenfrequency [22].

The only design parameter of the straight duct extensions with constant cross section is their length \mathcal{L}_x . Neglecting the effect of mean flow¹, the phase shift induced by shifting the in-/outlet termination by the distance \mathcal{L}_x depends linearly on the frequency ω

$$\angle R_{x,rig} = -\frac{2\omega\mathcal{L}_x}{c}. \quad (6)$$

¹axial mean flow can be accounted for by changing the propagation speed of f to $\bar{u} + c$ and g to $\bar{u} - c$

Figure 5: $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m=1,d}$ from Fig. 12 (black) compared to $\angle R_{d,rig}$ adapted by straight duct extension (red) and Helmholtz resonator (blue). Both elements are designed for $\nu_d = 100$ Hz.

In order to shape the frequency response of the Helmholtz resonator, four main design parameters are available: lengths l_1 and l_2 and cross sections S_1 and S_2 of the resonator neck and volume, respectively. Additional design parameters that are not considered here could be the purge mass flow rate and temperature.

Computing the exact frequency response of Helmholtz resonators depending on the mentioned design parameters requires sophisticated numerical or experimental methods [22]. However, in practice the same type of acoustic model will be used to obtain $\angle R_{x,rig}$ and $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,x}$. In case the employed acoustic model does not include certain effects that might be relevant in practice, they are neglected in both computed $\angle R_{x,rig}$ and $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,x}$. Thus, for the present purpose, comparably crude modeling approaches such as the Helmholtz equation employed in this study might be sufficient to compute $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ and to design the passive acoustic elements. In a later section we discuss how effects neglected in the employed acoustic models may compromise the proposed strategy.

Figure 5 exemplarily shows $\angle R_{d,rig}$ adapted by duct extension (blue line) and Helmholtz resonator (red line) to match $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m=1,d}$ taken from Fig. 12 at a design frequency of $\nu_d = \omega_d/2\pi = 100$ Hz. From Fig. 5 it becomes apparent, that the Helmholtz resonator is more appropriate to match the equivalent reflection coefficient shown. Due to its four degrees of freedom it can be designed to well approximate \mathcal{R}_m in a quite large frequency range around ν_d . In contrast, the straight duct extension matches \mathcal{R}_m only directly at ν_d .

In order to use a single-can test-rig to study the thermoacoustic stability properties and possibly the limit cycle (LC) of mode order m of a full can-annular combustor, $R_{x,rig}$ has to be designed to

match $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ at the dominant (respectively most unstable) frequencies of the full engine. However, these design frequencies are normally not known *a priori*. Even if the pure acoustic eigenfrequencies might be known from an acoustic model, the (generally unknown) flame dynamics may alter these frequencies. Furthermore, intrinsic thermoacoustic (ITA) modes may play an important role [23–25]. Their frequencies are not predictable without knowledge of the flame dynamics. Therefore, the passive acoustic elements in general have to be adapted in an iterative procedure, which ensures that the dominant frequency observed in the single-can test-rig converges to the dominant frequency of the full engine of a given azimuthal mode order m . A strategy is presented in the following section.

If the initial design of the Helmholtz resonator is good enough to approximate the relevant frequency range sufficiently well, as shown in Fig. 5, iterative adaption may not be necessary. However, the large number of degrees of freedom complicates the search for an optimal design, while this is straightforward for the duct extension. In the present case, the parameters of the resonator were chosen such that the design frequency is well above the Helmholtz mode and below the first axial mode, which coincide with the abrupt phase transitions at 40 Hz and 355 Hz, respectively. Sufficiently far away from the resonator eigenfrequencies, its damping rates are expected to be comparably small [22]. While the design works properly for the present case, a general design guideline is not immediately obvious and the set of parameters has to be optimized from case to case. In the following we therefore investigate the capabilities of both element types based on numerical models of single-can test-rig and full can-annular combustor.

Iterative adaption of passive elements

As discussed in the previous section, the frequency ν_d for which the Helmholtz resonator or the straight duct extension are initially designed to fulfill Eqn. (5) does in general not coincide with the dominant frequencies of the full engine. We therefore propose a fixed point iteration strategy with the objective that the dominant frequency observed in the single-can test-rig approaches the dominant frequency of the full engine for a given mode order m .

At this point, the terminology *dominant frequency* has to be defined more clearly. In case of an unstable system, the dominant frequency is clearly visible as a narrow peak in the measured

pressure spectrum (corresponds to LC frequency). For a stable system, the peaks in the pressure spectrum are broadened. However, the eigenmodes of the stable system still show up as maxima in the measured pressure spectrum. The peaks result from resonances of broad-band combustion noise emitted by the turbulent flame with stable eigenmodes of the system [26]. Thus, we define *dominant frequency* generally as the position of maxima in the sound pressure spectrum, no matter whether they appear as narrow or broad peaks.

Step zero of the proposed strategy is to compute the equivalent reflection coefficients $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ of the full can-annular combustor as defined in the previous section. If Helmholtz resonators are employed for the test-rig adaption, the initial parameters for a given m are selected to optimally approximate $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ in the relevant frequency range. The passive acoustic elements installed at the test-rig are designed to fulfill Eqn. (5) at an initial guess ν^0 of the dominant frequency of the full engine. For both, computing $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ and designing the elements, an acoustic solver, e.g. based on the Helmholtz equation, is employed.

The following steps of the proposed approach are:

1. Run the adapted test-rig and measure the dominant frequency ν^n .
2. Adapt the installed passive acoustic elements to fulfill Eqn. (5) at the measured frequency ν^n .
3. Iterate until the dominant frequency ν^n measured in the test-rig stays constant. Repeat with different m .

Unconditional convergence of the proposed iterative algorithm can not be proven, as in practice a comprehensive mathematical description of all sub-systems is not available. However, for all setups investigated in the present study, the algorithm converged even for initial frequencies ν^0 far away from the final value. This suggests, that the algorithm will converge for practically relevant cases.

In order to minimize the number of iterations necessary to adapt the passive elements, the initial frequency guess ν^0 should be as close to the dominant frequency for mode order m of the full system as possible. Due to the clustering of eigenmodes in typical can-annular combustors (see Fig. 7), the dominant frequencies of the individual azimuthal mode orders are generally close to each other [13]. Thus, the dominant frequency obtained for a certain m may serve as ν^0 for the next

higher m . In case the single-can test-rig comprises an entire sector of the considered can-annular combustor (including the corresponding part of the compressor plenum and the annular gap), it represents mode order $m = 0$ of the full engine and can be used to obtain the dominant frequency for $m = 0$. Alternatively, if known from an acoustic model, the pure acoustic eigenfrequency of the considered m can be used as initial guess v^0 . In many cases, flame dynamics do not affect the acoustic eigenmode drastically and it can thus be considered as good approximation of the thermoacoustic eigenmode. This however is not the case if the dominant mode is of ITA origin [24].

The relative change of dominant frequency Δv^n between iteration $n - 1$ and n may be used to define a convergence criterion:

$$\Delta v^n = \frac{|v^n - v^{n-1}|}{v^n} < \varepsilon. \quad (7)$$

If Δv^n is smaller than a predefined threshold ε , the iterations are stopped. An additional criterion based on the relative change of design parameters of the adapted elements may be used to distinguish slow progress from actual convergence of the algorithm. Although we cannot strictly prove that meeting these criteria is *always* sufficient for convergence of the algorithm, in all cases investigated in the present study criterion (7) correctly indicated convergence.

If the test-rig is adapted by means of straight duct extensions, only the lengths \mathcal{L}_x are available to fulfill Eqn. (5) at the observed dominant frequency. If Helmholtz resonators are used, at least the four geometrical parameters mentioned in the previous section are available for the adaption process. In the present work, we only modify one single parameter during the iteration process. In general, more sophisticated adaption strategies that modify multiple parameters at once in order to optimally approximate $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{R}_{m,x}}$ around v^n are conceivable. Deriving such strategies could be part of a follow-up study.

APPLICATION TO NETWORK MODEL OF A GENERIC CAN-ANNULAR COMBUSTOR

Within this section we demonstrate test-rig adaption for a generic can-annular combustor using straight duct extensions. Both, full configuration and adapted test-rig, are modeled by a quasi-1D

Figure 6: Network model of considered generic can-annular combustor.

thermo-acoustic network model. Results of the full configuration serve as a benchmark for the adapted test-rig. For the adaption using Helmholtz resonators, 3D effects might play a role. Consequently, this strategy is discussed in the next section, where a full 3D configuration is considered.

Setup

Figure 6 shows the network model of one unit cell of the generic can-annular combustor considered in the present section. The network model contains only 1D elements. The extension of the combustor in azimuthal direction is taken into account by a T-junction at the outlet. For simplicity we focus on matching only the downstream reflection coefficient $\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$, but the approach could equally be applied to adapt both up- and downstream termination simultaneously. The upstream reflection coefficient of the individual cans is set to $R_u = -0.8$ in order to take into account acoustic losses present in realistic systems. The dimensions and physical conditions of the system (cf. Fig. 6) are set in accordance with typical can-annular combustors. Fluid properties of air are used. The transition towards the turbine, which is often a choked nozzle in actuality, is represented by $R_{\text{turb}} = 1$ [21].

Flame dynamics are modeled by a flame transfer function (FTF) of a swirl burner test-rig taken from [27]. The dimensions of the flame and the mean flow speed in this test-rig are comparable to realistic can-annular combustors, although the employed FTF was measured at atmospheric conditions. Full engine and adapted test-rig model are compared based on their LC frequency and amplitude, because these are the most relevant quantities in practice. The iterative algorithm to adapt the test-rig model is also based on LC frequencies, as these corresponds to the *dominant*

frequencies measured experimentally. In order to capture the formation of LC oscillations we introduce a generic saturation factor s that models the amplitude dependence of the flame response F [28]

$$F(\omega, a) = \frac{\hat{Q}(\omega, a)}{\hat{u}} = s(a)\text{FTF}(\omega), \quad s(a) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{16(a-0.5)}}. \quad (8)$$

Here, \hat{Q} and \hat{u} denote the Fourier transform of the heat release rate and acoustic velocity at the reference position of the FTF and a is a measure of the amplitude level. The network models of the full can-annular combustor and the adapted single-can system are built and solved using the tool *taX*² [29]. The LC amplitude level a_{LC} , which corresponds to a growth rate $\sigma = 0$ of the most unstable system eigenmode, is calculated using a gradient based root search algorithm. The corresponding LC frequency is obtained by computing the eigenfrequencies of the network model with a saturation factor of $s(a_{LC})$.

Results of the full configuration

Figure 7 shows the eigenfrequencies of the full can-annular combustor with saturation factor $s(a_{LC})$ for all azimuthal mode orders m . The clustering of eigenmodes of different m is clearly visible [13]. Among the clusters shown one can identify an axial quarter-wave, three-quarter-wave, and five-quarter-wave mode. All modes in the quarter-wave cluster are unstable. The LC amplitude level a_{LC} and frequency is determined separately for each mode order m .

As a_{LC} is calculated separately for each m , any nonlinear interaction of individual mode orders m is neglected. Furthermore, the proposed approach of identifying equivalent reflection coefficients for the individual azimuthal mode orders assumes that those can be studied separately. In reality, at finite amplitude levels different azimuthal mode orders can interact, which may result in one dominant mode with LC frequency and amplitude level different from the values computed here. Additionally, the computed a_{LC} relies on Bloch-symmetry, which assumes that discrete rotational symmetry is retained even for finite amplitude levels [28]. This is not necessarily the case in

²code available at <https://gitlab.lrz.de/tfd/tax>
M. Haeringer, GTP-20-1545

Figure 7: Eigenfrequencies for all azimuthal mode orders m of full can-annular combustor at a_{LC} . The corresponding amplitude levels are in the range $a_{LC} = 0.59 - 0.65$.

practice. However, for the proposed approach, it is not crucial to exactly predict the LC amplitude and frequency that results from the interaction of multiple unstable modes and that is potentially influenced by a symmetry break. In case the proposed approach indicates a thermoacoustic instability at only *one single* azimuthal mode order, the combustor has to be re-designed anyway. Thus, it is not necessary to correctly represent the case of multiple unstable mode orders and accurately predict the exact amplitude level a_{LC} .

The equivalent reflection coefficient $\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ of the considered can-annular combustor is defined at the location indicated in Fig. 6 and shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 3.

Iterative adaption of the test-rig model

In the following we illustrate the adaption procedure for the “push-pull” mode $m = 8$. For all other mode orders the procedure is exactly equivalent and we just show the final results. We use the LC frequency $\nu_1^0 = 66\text{Hz}$ of $m = 0$ as initial frequency guess. This is the dominant frequency that would be measured in the single-can test-rig without any extensions. In order to demonstrate the robustness of the proposed approach, we repeat the procedure with an initial frequency of $\nu_2^0 = 300\text{Hz}$ which is quite far away from the dominant frequency for $m = 8$. According to Eqn. (6), the corresponding initial extension lengths are $\mathcal{L}_{d,1}^0 = 4.33\text{ m}$ for ν_1^0 and $\mathcal{L}_{d,2}^0 = 1.26\text{ m}$ for ν_2^0 .

Figure 8 shows $\angle\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ for the considered azimuthal mode order $m = 8$ together with the phase of the outlet reflection coefficient of the test-rig $\angle R_{d,\text{rig}}$ for the individual iterations. Starting the

Figure 8: $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m=8,d}$ (black curve) together with $\angle R_{d,rig}$ for the individual iterations. Phase for initial lengths shown in black, solid lines indicate iterations for $\nu^0 = 66$ Hz dashed lines for $\nu^0 = 300$ Hz.

Figure 9: LC frequencies of the test-rig for individual iterations with $\nu^0 = 66$ Hz (colored crosses), LC frequency for initial extension length marked with black crosses. Black square indicates LC frequency of the full engine for $m = 8$.

iterations at $\nu_1^0 = 66$ Hz, the process takes five steps until a prescribed $\Delta \nu < 0.5\%$ is reached. This is a very strict criterion that could probably be weakened in practice. However, here we want to demonstrate the accuracy that can be achieved by the proposed approach.

Figure 9 shows the corresponding LC frequencies ν^n observed in the test-rig model for the individual iterations. Within five iterations the LC frequency $\nu^5 = 103.0$ Hz matches the LC frequency of $m = 8$ of the full engine with a relative error below 0.2%. The obtained LC amplitude level after convergence is $a_{LC} = 0.594$, which is the same value as for the full can-annular combustor. The final extension length is $\mathcal{L}_d^5 = 3.06$ m.

Note that, if the criterion in Eqn. (7) is weakened to $\Delta \nu < 5\%$, which is more a realistic value due to limited measurement accuracy, the approach converges already after two iterations. In

Figure 10: Normalized absolute value and phase of acoustic pressure and axial velocity in test-rig can with extension (dashed black) and in can of full engine (blue) for $m = 8$ plotted over the axial coordinate z .

this case the relative error of the test-rig LC frequency is below 3 %, while the relative error in LC amplitude level is approx. 2 %.

If $v_2^0 = 300$ Hz, which is far away from the actual LC frequency of the full engine, is used as initial frequency guess, the process converges after six iterations for $\Delta v < 0.5$ % and after three iterations for $\Delta v < 5$ %, while the achieved accuracy is comparable to that of v_1^0 .

Figure 10 compares the mode shapes in one can predicted by the respective network model of the full engine and the adapted test-rig. Inside the can the acoustic pressure and velocity of the full engine and the single-can test-rig agree well.

The procedure illustrated for $m = 8$ is completely analogous for all other azimuthal mode orders. The dominant frequency $\nu = 66$ Hz of $m = 0$ is used as an initial guess for all mode orders. For each m , the approach converges within a maximum of five iterations, while the relative errors in LC frequency and amplitude levels are below 1 %. If a weakened convergence criterion $\Delta v < 5$ % is used, the approach converges within two iterations for each mode order m . Table 1 shows the resulting extension lengths for each mode order m .

Stability properties of the adapted test-rig

In the previous section we pointed out that a single-can test-rig model can be adapted iteratively to show the same LC as the full configuration at a given azimuthal mode order³. So far, we

³ provided that Bloch-symmetry holds and nonlinear interaction of individual mode orders is negligible

have not discussed the stability properties of the adapted test-rig model. A LC is characterized by $\sigma = 0$, while the (linear) stability of the system is determined by the sign of σ in the zero-amplitude limit $a = 0$. The passive acoustic elements are designed such that Eqn. (5) holds for *purely real-valued* design frequencies ω_d ($\sigma = 0$). For $\sigma \neq 0$, Eqn. (5) does not hold in general. Thus, even if the LC frequencies of test-rig and full engine match, the eigenfrequencies in the zero-amplitude limit are generally not identical.

We can however argue, that for a unique, stable LC to develop, the modal growth rate must be $\sigma > 0$ in the zero-amplitude limit. Provided that both systems develop an identical LC, both systems must be linearly unstable with $\sigma > 0$ in the zero-amplitude limit. To conclude, both adapted test-rig and full engine will have the same stability properties, although their eigenmodes do not necessarily have the same frequency and growth rate in the zero-amplitude limit.

Critical assessment of the adaption strategy

The converged extension lengths for the individual mode orders shown in Tbl. 1 are quite large compared to the length of the can. This will cause problems for the practical implementation of this strategy if the evaluated extension length can not be realized in the high-pressure test-bench.

Figure 10 illustrates exemplarily for $m = 8$, why the extension has to be that long. $\mathcal{R}_{m=8,d}$ could be approximated by an acoustically soft termination at axial position $z = 3.2$ m in Fig. 10 (pressure node). In this case, the mode in the full engine would be approximated by a half-wave mode in the test-rig. However, as $R_{\text{turb}} = 1$ at the end of the extension is fixed, the full engine mode has to be approximated by a three-quarter-wave mode, which results in large \mathcal{L}_d . It is apparent that in this case there exists also a lower frequency quarter-wave mode in the test-rig. This mode is observed in Fig. 9 at frequency $\nu = 34$ Hz. It has no counterpart in the full engine and can be seen as an artifact of the proposed method (in the following also called “spurious mode”).

This mode may become dominant in the test-rig, which causes ambiguity on which measured frequency the iterations should be based on. However, a general criterion can be formulated. We define the phase being wrapped in the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$: If $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d} > 0$, the full engine mode is approximated by a three-quarter-wave mode, i.e. the iterations must be based on the second mode of the test-rig. If $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d} \leq 0$, the full engine mode is approximated by a quarter-wave mode and the

iterations must be based on the first mode of the test-rig. However, if for $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d} > 0$ the spurious mode is unstable in the test-rig, it will be difficult or even impossible to identify the frequency of the second mode on which the iterations have to be based on. Additionally, if the spurious mode is unstable and dominates for the final extension length, the stability of the full engine mode can not be assessed with the adapted test-rig.

The final extension lengths in Tbl. 1 are not directly related to any characteristic length of the combustor. Thus, they can not be deduced from geometrical consideration, as it is current practice. Instead, iterative adjustment according to the proposed strategy is necessary. This, however, would be very costly in high-pressure test-rigs. The high-pressure cell has to be opened for each iteration step and for each mode order. If instead of a single operating condition with a fixed dominant frequency, an entire operating window with variable dominant frequencies is investigated, the effort of implementing such an iterative strategy will be prohibitive.

In summary, the iterative test-rig adaption demonstrated within this section is most likely impractical, but when using straight duct extensions there is no obvious alternative to the proposed iterative strategy.

VALIDATION WITH A CONFIGURATION OF APPLIED RELEVANCE

Within this section we demonstrate test-rig adaption using Helmholtz resonators for a can-annular combustor with 16 cans modeled by the 3D inhomogeneous Helmholtz equation. The objective is to demonstrate the proposed test-rig adaption for a configuration that could similarly be found in practice (e.g. see [6]). Again, results from the adapted single-can system are compared to the full can-annular combustor model.

Setup

Fig. 11 shows a slice through one sector of the considered setup along the axial direction. Flame dynamics are represented by the flame model shown in Eqn. (8) of the previous section [27]. They are coupled to the acoustics by a source term that is active in the flame region indicated in Fig. 11. The flame divides the domain into a cold ($T_c = 780$ K) and hot ($T_h = 1800$ K) region. Fluid properties of air are used. BBCs are imposed at the cutting interface of plenum and annular gap.

Figure 11: 3D model of realistic can-annular combustor. Individual cans are coupled via plenum and annular gap. Colors show normalized $|\hat{p}|$ for the dominant mode of azimuthal order $m = 1$.

The acoustic terminations towards compressor and turbine are set to $R_{\text{comp}} = R_{\text{turb}} = 1$. To account for acoustic damping, which is not included in the Helmholtz equation, we assume that a LC is established at a positive modal growth rate of $\sigma = 2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ [30]. The model is built and solved using the finite element software COMSOL Multiphysics [31].

Equivalent reflection coefficient

Due to non-planar acoustic waves in the vicinity of the annular gap and the plenum-can transition, the equivalent reflection coefficients $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ are defined in some axial distance to the azimuthal coupling interfaces (see Fig. 11). They are obtained by computing the forced response of the plenum and annular gap section at discrete frequencies for individual m .

Figure 12 shows $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ of the plenum (top) and $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ of the annular gap (bottom) versus $\text{He} = \omega d/c$. For better visibility, only $m = 0, 1, 2, 8$ of $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ is shown. The characteristic length d is set to the can-can distance at the annular gap, i.e. 1/16th of the total annular gap perimeter. The relevant frequencies of the first axial mode order are in the range $\text{He} \approx \pi/14 \dots \pi/6$.

The equivalent reflection coefficient of the annular gap $\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ is in good agreement with that obtained from the network model shown in Fig. 3. Compared to the network model case, the individual values of $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ are more distinct from each other (due to a larger A in the present configuration), which indicates that the cluster of first axial mode order is not as closely spaced as in Fig. 7. The overall linear decrease of $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ with frequency reflects the axial distance of $\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ to the annular gap.

Figure 12: Equivalent reflection coefficient of 3D configuration. $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ for $m = 0, 1, 2, 8$ (top) and $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ (bottom) vs. Helmholtz-number He .

At first glance, $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ looks notably different from that in Fig. 3 and its behavior seems quite chaotic. The abrupt phase changes observed in Fig. 12 are related to eigenfrequencies of the plenum. As explained for Fig. 3, at these eigenfrequencies, the equivalent reflection coefficient equals $\mathcal{R}_{m,u} = 1$. In case of the quasi-1D network model, the plenum eigenfrequencies are regularly spaced, resulting in a regular behavior of $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ as shown in Fig. 3. In the present configuration, the plenum is a large volume of complex shape, which features irregularly spaced eigenfrequencies with complex 3D mode shapes. In particular for higher frequencies ($He > 3\pi/8$) the eigenfrequencies are closely spaced. However, except for the immediate vicinity of these plenum eigenfrequencies, $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ for all m closely follow a common trend, which linearly decreases from π . This linear decrease results from the axial distance of $\mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ to the can-plenum transition. Thus, except for very low frequencies $He < \pi/16$ and the immediate vicinity of plenum eigenfrequencies, all mode orders impose an almost ideal open end at the can inlet.

Importance of upstream coupling

Except for the immediate vicinity of plenum eigenfrequencies, the individual $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ are closely spaced in the frequency range $He \approx \pi/16 \dots 3\pi/8$ that is relevant for the first axial mode order. In particular, $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ are much closer together than the individual $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ in the same frequency range. The phase $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m=0,u}$ of the uncoupled $m = 0$ configuration is thus a good approximation for all other

azimuthal mode orders, except near plenum eigenfrequencies. This indicates that for most of the relevant frequency range, the coupling via the annular gap is much more important than the coupling via the plenum.

To substantiate this argumentation, we compare LC amplitude levels and frequencies of the full system and a system coupled at the downstream side only ($m = 0$ set at the plenum interfaces) in Tbl. 2. All frequencies are normalized by the LC frequency of the $m = 0$ system. The azimuthal mode order $m = 5$ is stable, thus a_{LC} is undefined there. As observed in Tbl. 2, the relative difference of the two configurations in terms of LC amplitude level and frequency is below 5% for all mode orders, except for ν of $m = 2$ and a_{LC} of $m = 6$. The LC frequency of azimuthal mode order $m = 2$ is close to a plenum eigenfrequency visible in Fig. 12 at $He \approx \pi/10$. This explains the differences between fully-coupled and downstream-only-coupled systems for this mode order m . To conclude, for the present configuration can-can coupling via the plenum is negligible for frequencies that are not in the immediate vicinity of plenum eigenfrequencies. In the following we will therefore only consider adaption of the downstream termination. The error of representing the upstream termination by the uncoupled plenum ($m = 0$) is considered to be small compared to other possible error sources.

However, this finding can not be generalized for all practical relevant systems. The investigated setup does not have cross-fire tubes, which would directly connect the cans upstream of the flame. These could drastically increase the upstream coupling of the individual cans, which would have to be accounted for in the same manner as shown for the downstream termination.

Matching downstream termination

The initial design of the Helmholtz resonator with the considered four degrees of freedom (cf. Fig. 4) is non-trivial. However, the four parameters allow approximating $\mathcal{L}\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ well for a wide frequency range. Due to the high computational effort when searching a four-dimensional parameter space for an optimal design, we only consider $m = 1$ and $m = 8$. However, the strategy can be applied accordingly to all other mode orders.

As indicated in Fig. 5 and discussed below, for a good match with $\mathcal{L}\mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ the Helmholtz mode of the resonator should be well below the relevant frequency range, while the first axial mode should

Figure 13: $\angle R_{\text{rig},d}$ adapted with Helmholtz resonator for $m = 8$ (top) and $m = 1$ (bottom) together with $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ of respective m (black dashed).

be well above. To shift the Helmholtz mode to low frequencies, the resonator volume should be as large as the limitations of the high-pressure cell allow. However, the length of the volume l_2 is bounded by the lower frequency limit of the axial mode. The above guidelines are common for all mode orders m . The two remaining design parameters l_1 and S_1 are used to optimally approximate $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ for the given m .

Figure 13 shows $\angle R_{\text{rig},d}$ adapted with Helmholtz resonators designed for $m = 8$ (top) and $m = 1$ (bottom) compared to $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ of the respective mode orders. The resonators are mounted at the azimuthal interfaces of the annular gap. The parameters chosen for $m = 1$ and $m = 8$ are summarized in Tbl. 3. The parameters l_1 and A_1 (respectively for $m = 8$ and $m = 1$), for which a range is specified, are employed for the iterative adaption. For $m = 1$ $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ can be approximated very well for a wide frequency range. To achieve comparable accuracy for $m = 8$, the necessary resonator volume would have to be even larger than the present one, which is not considered to be realistic. In general, the achievable accuracy crucially depends on the set of parameters that is realizable in the available test-bench.

The resonators are initially designed to exactly represent $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ at the LC frequency of the respective lower mode order. This results in initial parameters $A_1 = 0.04$ for $m = 1$ and $l_1 = 0.03$ m for $m = 8$. With a convergence criterion $\Delta v < 0.5\%$ the adaption algorithm immediately converges with the initial resonator design for $m = 8$. For $m = 1$ convergence is reached after the first iteration

Figure 14: Normalized $|\hat{p}|$ of dominant mode in single-can test-rig model adapted with Helmholtz resonator for $m = 1$.

with an updated $A_1 = 0.045$. The normalized LC frequencies and amplitude levels obtained with the adapted test-rig models are $\nu = 1.09$ and $a_{LC} = 0.67$ for $m = 1$ and $\nu = 1.86$ and $a_{LC} = 0.48$ for $m = 8$. Thus, the relative error compared to the downstream only coupled system is below 1% regarding LC frequency and below 5% regarding amplitude level. The relative error in LC frequency compared to the fully coupled configuration is below 5% (cf. Tbl. 2). The normalized LC $|\hat{p}|$ obtained from the test-rig model adapted for $m = 1$ is shown in Fig. 14 and agrees well with $|\hat{p}|$ of $m = 1$ of the full configuration shown in Fig. 11. The outline of the adapted resonator is also visible in Fig. 14.

Critical assessment of adaption strategy

Test-rig adaption by means of Helmholtz resonators seems much more practicable than using duct extensions. Due to the good initial agreement of $\angle R_{\text{rig,d}}$ and $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ over a wide frequency range, the number of iterations necessary to adapt the resonator is very small, iterations might even be avoided altogether. At the same time it is possible to investigate entire operating windows with variable dominant frequencies without having to re-design the up-/downstream terminations for each operating condition.

The design parameters of the considered resonator appear to be much easier accessible than the length of duct extensions. It should be possible to change the neck length and cross section remotely, without opening the high-pressure cell. Other design parameters not considered here, like the purge flow temperature, should be easily accessible, too.

The Helmholtz resonators will also introduce “spurious” modes that are not present in the full combustor. However, as their eigenfrequencies are related to the Helmholtz-mode of the resonator, they will be strongly damped and are expected to play a minor role.

A main drawback of this element type is that there is no generalized design guideline yet. The initial design and the iteration strategy have to be adjusted from case to case. Part of future work might be to develop an optimal iteration strategy that changes multiple parameters at once. Another drawback is the large size of the adapted resonators. In case the optimized initial resonator design does not fit in the high-pressure cell, the test-rig adaption will again rely more on the iterative algorithm. Furthermore, it is not yet clear how strong the damping of the resonator (which is designed to be small in the relevant frequency range) will affect the thermoacoustic properties of the test-rig.

INFLUENCE OF EFFECTS NEGLECTED IN COMBUSTOR MODEL

The strategy proposed in the present work is only demonstrated with thermoacoustic models. The models used do not account for non-acoustic effects like heat transfer, entropy waves and mean flow (in the Helmholtz solver). Furthermore, acoustic damping is only modeled in a simplistic way, i.e. by means of non-ideal boundary conditions in the network model and by assuming uniformly distributed damping in the 3D configuration (which is equivalent to setting the LC growth-rate to $\sigma > 0$ [30]). Acoustic boundary conditions towards turbine and compressor are idealized.

These effects neglected in the present models will generally affect the thermoacoustic properties of the considered systems. However, it is important to note that in the present study these effects are neglected in *both* the test-rig model and the model of the full configuration. In reality those effects will in turn be present in *both* configurations. We do not aim to accurately model a real combustor configuration. Instead, we demonstrate the correspondence between adapted test-rig and full configuration.

To assess the importance of effects neglected in the thermoacoustic models of the present study, we thus have to focus on the parts where test-rig and full configuration differ, i.e. the up-/downstream terminations of the can. In particular at the downstream termination, neglected

effects related to entropy fluctuations, mean flow and localized acoustic damping might have different influences on the thermoacoustic properties of test-rig and full engine.

In case duct extensions are used for test-rig adaption, the convective time delay relevant for entropy waves is drastically increased. Also the Helmholtz resonator might be affected by entropy waves. However, due to the generally large convective time delays in realistic combustor configurations, effects caused by entropy waves typically occur at very low frequencies and are thus well separable from purely acoustic effects considered in the present study.

The elements installed upstream the first turbine stator vanes may change the non-acoustic flow properties, which in turn affects R_{turb} . For example the cooling of the duct extension or the purge flow through the Helmholtz resonator may change mean flow temperature and velocity. However, the expected changes of the mean flow are very small and so is the influence on R_{turb} .

Acoustic damping localized at the annular gap in the full engine and at the Helmholtz resonator in the adapted test-rig is only taken into account in the simplistic way mentioned above. With the methods employed in the present study we cannot quantify the influence of this localized acoustic damping on the thermoacoustics of test-rig and full engine. This has to be addressed by more sophisticated numerical models and/or by experimental validation of the proposed strategy.

CONCLUSION

The present study discusses strategies to adapt single-can combustion test-rigs to reproduce the thermoacoustic properties of a full can-annular combustor. The coupling of the individual cans inside the can-annular combustor can be lumped into equivalent reflection coefficients $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ (with $x \hat{=} u/d$) up- and downstream of a single can. If correct values of $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ can be imposed at the up-/downstream terminations of a single-can test-rig, the rig mimics the thermoacoustic properties of the full engine.

We exploit the discrete rotational symmetry of typical can-annular combustors and employ Bloch-wave theory to obtain $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$. These reflection coefficients induce a frequency dependent phase shift, which generally depends on the coupling interfaces, the azimuthal mode order m and the number of cans, but not on the thermoacoustic properties of the individual cans.

Two types of passive acoustic elements, namely duct extensions of constant cross section and Helmholtz resonators, are employed to match the phase shift induced by $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ for given design frequencies. For both, computing $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ and designing the passive elements, an acoustic solver, e.g. based on the Helmholtz equation is employed. We propose an iterative strategy, which ensures that the design frequency converges to the dominant frequency of the given mode order of the full system. Following that approach, the single-can test-rig can be used to investigate each azimuthal mode order m of the full can-annular combustor in terms of stability, limit cycle frequencies and amplitude levels without *a priori* knowledge of relevant frequencies of the full engine.

The proposed strategy is applied to a network model of a generic can-annular combustor and to a 3D applied configuration modeled by the Helmholtz equation. For the latter we show that the coupling via the compressor exit plenum is negligible for frequencies that are not in the immediate vicinity of plenum eigenfrequencies. The test-rig models adapted following the proposed strategy mimic the full engine with comparably good accuracy for both considered element types. However, using Helmholtz resonators seems much more practical. Their design parameters are easier to access remotely and the geometrical dimensions of the adapted resonators are more reasonable than those of the duct extension. Most importantly, the up-/downstream reflection coefficient tuned by a Helmholtz resonator matches $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ for a wide frequency range. Thus, fewer or no iterations are necessary to adapt the resonator and one single resonator design may be employed to investigate an entire operating window.

The proposed strategy has been demonstrated only with numerical models and has yet to be validated experimentally.

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TABLES

Table 1: Extension lengths for individual azimuthal mode orders m .

m	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
\mathcal{L}_d [m]	6.12	5.31	4.51	3.89	3.49	3.24	3.10	3.06

Table 2: Normalized LC frequencies ν and amplitudes a_{LC} of individual m for fully-coupled “u/d” and downstream-only-coupled “d” configuration.

m	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
ν , u/d	1.14	1.17	1.40	1.49	1.74	1.81	1.85	1.86
ν , d	1.09	1.28	1.44	1.49	1.76	1.82	1.85	1.86
a_{LC} , u/d	0.66	0.63	0.56	0.42	–	0.47	0.50	0.51
a_{LC} , d	0.68	0.64	0.56	0.44	–	0.36	0.49	0.50

Table 3: Parameters of Helmholtz resonators fitted for $m = 1$ and $m = 8$.

	S_2/S_1	l_2 (m)	$A_1 = S_1/S_c$	l_1 (m)
$m = 1$	20	1.2	0.04 – 0.05	0.43
$m = 8$	20	1	0.4	0.02 – 0.04

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Generic can-annular combustor. Cans are coupled at up- and downstream side via compressor exit plenum and annular gap. R_{turb} and R_{comp} denote reflection coefficients of turbine inlet and compressor exit.

2. Definition of $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ at the in-/outlet of a single can. $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ are dependent on the azimuthal distance d of two cans and the cross sections of can S_c , annular gap S_a and compressor exit plenum S_p .
3. $\angle \mathcal{R}_m$ of generic 16-can combustor with two different area ratios $A = 20$ (top) and $A = 0.06$ (bottom) plotted vs. Helmholtz-number He .
4. Matching $\mathcal{R}_{m,x}$ of the full engine by extending the single-can test-rig with straight ducts (top) and by installing Helmholtz-resonators at the in-/outlet (bottom).
5. $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m=1,d}$ from Fig. 12 (black) compared to $\angle R_{d,rig}$ adapted by straight duct extension (red) and Helmholtz resonator (blue). Both elements are designed for $v_d = 100$ Hz.
6. Network model of considered generic can-annular combustor.
7. Eigenfrequencies for all azimuthal mode orders m of full can-annular combustor at a_{LC} . The corresponding amplitude levels are in the range $a_{LC} = 0.59 - 0.65$.
8. $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m=8,d}$ (black curve) together with $\angle R_{d,rig}$ for the individual iterations. Phase for initial lengths shown in black, solid lines indicate iterations for $v^0 = 66$ Hz dashed lines for $v^0 = 300$ Hz.
9. LC frequencies of the test-rig for individual iterations with $v^0 = 66$ Hz (colored crosses), LC frequency for initial extension length marked with black crosses. Black square indicates LC frequency of the full engine for $m = 8$.
10. Normalized absolute value and phase of acoustic pressure and axial velocity in test-rig can with extension (dashed black) and in can of full engine (blue) for $m = 8$ plotted over the axial coordinate z .
11. 3D model of realistic can-annular combustor. Individual cans are coupled via plenum and annular gap. Colors show normalized $|\hat{p}|$ for the dominant mode of azimuthal order $m = 1$.
12. Equivalent reflection coefficient of 3D configuration. $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,u}$ for $m = 0, 1, 2, 8$ (top) and $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ (bottom) vs. Helmholtz-number He .
13. $\angle R_{rig,d}$ adapted with Helmholtz resonator for $m = 8$ (top) and $m = 1$ (bottom) together with $\angle \mathcal{R}_{m,d}$ of respective m (black dashed).
14. Normalized $|\hat{p}|$ of dominant mode in single-can test-rig model adapted with Helmholtz resonator for $m = 1$.